

D6.5 - FINAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

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Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process.

The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and bio-based systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

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PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	x
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to SUSTRACK project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

SUSTRACK Consortium

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4	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PC	SK
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6	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	UGENT	BE
7	FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	TECNALIA	ES
8	FVA SAS DI LOUIS FERRINI & C	FVA	IT
9	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	UNIFE	IT
10	BUNDESANSTALT FÜR MATERIALFORSCHUNG UND - PRUEFUNG	BAM	DE
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable D6.5 provides an update on the progress of dissemination, communication, and stakeholder engagement tools and activities implemented between M19 and M36 of the SUSTRACK project (May 2024 - October 2025). It builds upon the strategies, methodologies, channels, materials, and tools initially defined in D6.1 “Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan” and further detailed in D6.2.

During this period, several dissemination and communication tools have been further developed, updated, and enriched, including the project website, flyers, posters, roll-ups, videos, publications, factsheets, promotional banners, thematic cards, press releases, toolkits, and dedicated social media campaigns.

A wide range of dissemination and communication activities was carried out with the active contribution of all partners. These included conferences, meetings, and large-scale events involving citizens, young people, and the general public; educational events with university students; as well as collaborations with other projects and initiatives. Several online activities complemented these efforts, further enhancing the project’s outreach and visibility. Special attention was given to ensuring that SUSTRACK’s results reached both specialised stakeholders and broader audiences, reinforcing the project’s impact across multiple sectors.

Stakeholder engagement has remained a central pillar of SUSTRACK. From M19 to M36, the project intensified efforts to involve key actors through conferences, co-creation workshops, interviews, surveys, and meetings. These activities were instrumental in producing and disseminating SUSTRACK’s final results, while ensuring that stakeholder perspectives contributed to the formulation of actionable policy recommendations for advancing the circular bio-based transition.

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List of Abbreviations	
Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
ANP	Analytic Network Process
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MML	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

D6.1 “Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan” defined the overall strategies, methodologies, channels, materials and tools for effective project dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement. Based on this initial framework, D6.2 provided the first progress report, covering activities from the beginning of the project to M18.

This deliverable, D6.5, builds upon that foundation and presents the progress made during the second reporting period (M19-M36). It updates on:

- the dissemination and communication (D&C) tools that have been further developed, enriched and adapted to the evolving needs of the project, as well as on the wide range of D&C activities carried out by all partners to maximise visibility, outreach and impact;
- the stakeholder engagement activities implemented, which remained a key driver to validate results and ensure the active involvement of relevant actors;
- the clustering and collaboration activities with other EU-funded projects and relevant initiatives, highlighting synergies, joint actions and opportunities for knowledge exchange.

The structure of this deliverable mirrors that of D6.2 for consistency, but places emphasis on the results achieved in the second reporting period, the lessons learnt, and the recommendations for the final phase of SUSTRACK, ensuring that communication, dissemination and engagement activities effectively supported the achievement of the project’s objectives.

This deliverable is divided into 5 main sections:

- Chapter 2 provides an overview of the **dissemination and communication tools** which have been created in the second reporting period (M19-M36) of the SUSTRACK project;
- Chapter 3 provides an overview of the **dissemination and communication activities** implemented by all partners in the second reporting period (M19-M36) of the SUSTRACK project;
- Chapter 4 provides an overview of the **stakeholder engagement activities** implemented in the second reporting period (M19-M36) of the SUSTRACK project;
- Chapter 5 provides an overview of the activities implemented in the second reporting period (M19-M36) of the SUSTRACK project, to foster **collaboration with relevant projects and initiatives**.
- Finally, Chapter 6 provides conclusions.

2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS

To support the SUSTRACK project dissemination and communication activities, several tools have been designed, based on the strategy defined in D6.1, targeting different target audiences.

A primary and a secondary target audience have been identified in D6.1, to be reached throughout the project, including respectively:

- Primary targets: Policy, Business and financial ecosystem, Research and innovation community, Sustainability system community, Multipliers, Other EU-funded projects and initiatives;
- Secondary targets: Civil society, Media.

All the dissemination and communication tools have been made available for the consortium members in their latest versions on the shared repository, to facilitate easy access.

2.1 Overview of Dissemination and Communication channels and tools

Table 1 lists all the channels and tools envisaged for the project with the KPIs to be achieved, the delivery month (also see D6.1 for detailed information) and the KPIs reached by M36 (in light green background are highlighted the dissemination and communication channels and tools for which the KPIs have been completed).

Table 1 - SUSTRACK Dissemination and communication channels and tools

OVERVIEW OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS AND TOOLS				
Category	Channel/Tool	KPIs	KPI Reached	Target Audience
Brand identity	Brand identity kit (Logo, Templates, Guidelines)	#1 (M1)	#1 (M1)	All target audiences
SUSTRACK Website	Website	#1 (M3) with >10,000 visits from >25 countries	#1 (M1) with 27622 unique visitors from >105 countries (last update: 21/10/2025)	All target audiences
Promotional material	Flyers	#2, 500 distributed (M6-M24)	#6, 125 distributed in person + 1487 views online	All target audiences, but mainly primary targets

	Roll-ups	#2 (M6, M24)	#2	All target audiences, but mainly primary targets
	Posters	>2 (M6, M24)	#5	All target audiences, but mainly primary targets
	Presentations about the project and its achievements	On demand	#1	All target audiences
Publications and actionable knowledge	Publications	>6	#9 (in progress)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem • Research and innovation community • Sustainability system community
	Case study factsheets (one per each sector)	At least #4	#8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem • Research and innovation community • Sustainability system community
	Conference outcome factsheets	#3	#23	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem • Research and innovation community

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability system community
	Case studies videos (one per each sector)	At least #4	#4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem • Research and innovation community • Sustainability system community
	Infographic cards	#20	During the implementation of the project, given the nature of the results and the timing of their publication, it was considered more effective to produce instead more thematic cards, for a total number of #33 cards (KPI: #10).	All target audiences, but mainly primary targets
	Toolkits to make the actionable knowledge easily accessible to the stakeholders in the 6 target countries (IT, NL, SK, DE, BE, ES)	#6 toolkits	#6	Mainly primary targets in the 6 target countries
Multimedia	Promotional video	#1 (M8)	#1 (M1)	All target audiences
	Video teasers for Social Media campaigns	#2	#2	All target audiences
	Promotional banners	>10	#29	All target audiences

	Thematic cards	#10	#33	All target audiences
Dissemination and communication materials	Email campaigns	#10	#14	All target audiences
	Newsletters	>3 (M12, M24, M36)	#3 (M12, M24, M36)	All target audiences
	Press releases	>4 (M1, M12, M24, M36)	#4 (M1, M12, M24, M36)	All target audiences
Social Media	Social Media profiles (LinkedIn, Twitter X) Additional: YouTube	#2 (M3), >3000 followers, >1000 posts	#3 (M1), 5489 followers (last update: 30/10/2025), 429 posts. The KPI related to the number of social media posts was not fully achieved. This was due to a strategic choice to prioritise content directly linked to SUSTRACK's activities and results, rather than publishing more general news about the circular bioeconomy. The focus was therefore placed on ensuring that all communication outputs were relevant, high-quality, and consistent with the project's objectives and messaging, rather than on meeting quantitative targets.	All target audiences
	Social Media campaigns	>4	#5	All target audiences

2.2 Brand identity kit

A recognisable visual identity was designed and produced at an early stage of the project's course. Detailed information about the brand identity kit was already delivered in D6.1.

2.3 Website

The first version of the [SUSTRACK website](#) was designed and deployed on M1. Detailed information about its design was already delivered in D6.1. Until the end of the project, SUSTRACK website was visited by 27622 unique visitors from >105 countries (last update 21/10/2025).

During the second reporting period, the website was updated and enriched with new materials, described below.

2.3.1 “Outcomes” section

The "Outcomes" section (Figure 1) has been constantly updated with new materials, to collect in an organised and easily accessible manner all the results and outcomes of the project. It currently includes the following subsections:

- [Case studies](#), with #2 factsheets and #1 video per sector
- [Toolkit](#), with #6 factsheets in 6 languages (#total of #36 factsheets), #2 capacity building webinars and #1 video summarising the main results achieved by the project
- [Monitoring system](#), with #841 visits - last update: 14/10/2025
- [Conference factsheets](#), with #23 factsheets
- [Publications](#)
- [Deliverables](#)
- [Communication materials](#)
- [Press release](#)
- [Newsletter](#)

Figure 1 - Screenshot of the "Outcomes" section on the SUSTRACK website

2.3.2 News page

The “News” section (Figure 2) was constantly updated, in order to have an overview of the main activities, achievements, conferences and events organised by SUSTRACK. Moreover, press releases and newsletters are also published in this section, maximising their diffusion through this channel. The news was also systematically published on all the social media channels to increase its impact and views.

Figure 2 - Screenshots of the "News" section on the SUSTRACK website

2.4 Promotional materials

2.4.1 Flyers and posters

At M25, [#5 new materials](#) were designed to present the main results of each Work Package. These materials were created to be used both as **flyers** and as **posters**, complementing the initial flyer developed at M6, and focusing on specific results rather than general project information.

Throughout the project, partners were encouraged to limit the printing of promotional materials, in line with the European Commission (EC)'s paperless guidelines, so the distribution of flyers has been limited. 100 flyers have been distributed at the BIOTRANSFORM booth in the context of EUBCE 2024 (see Section 3.1.3). Instead, the materials were made available on the project website and promoted through dedicated social media campaigns, maximising visibility while reducing environmental impact. Their dissemination achieved 1487 views.

Figure 3 - An example of the new SUSTRACK flyer/poster

2.4.2 Roll-ups

In parallel to flyers and posters, at M25 a new roll-up was created to present, in a concise way, the main results of each Work Package. The roll-up included QR codes linking to further in-depth materials available on the SUSTRACK website.

Figure 4 - New roll-up

2.4.3 Project presentation

A PowerPoint presentation about the project and its achievements (including objectives, expected outcomes...) has been designed at M5, ready to be customised by partners depending on the purpose. Detailed information was already included in D6.1.

2.5 Publications and actionable knowledge

2.5.1 Publications

Although publications are not the main objective, being SUSTRACK a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project, some partners have some publications published or in progress, deriving from the results of different tasks (Table 2).

Table 2 - List of SUSTRACK publications

Title	Authors	Journal	Status	Task/WP of ref.
<u>Barriers to transitioning to a circular bio-based economy: Findings from an industrial perspective</u>	Elina Dace, Alessandro Cascavilla, Marco Bianchi, Elisa Chioatto, Emy Zecca, Luana Ladu, Gülşah Yilan	Sustainable Production and Consumption	Published	T1.1
<u>Circular bioeconomy: A review of empirical practices across implementation scales</u>	Marco Bianchi, Alessandro Cascavilla, Janire Clavell Diaz, Luana Ladu, Barbara Palacino Blazquez, Menger Pierre, Eleonora Staffieri, Gülşah Yilan	Journal of Cleaner Production	Published	T2.1
<u>Mapping the Barriers to a Sustainable Transition: Insights from an Extensive Grey Literature Analysis and Focus Group Discussion</u>	Gülşah Yilan, Elina Dace, Mariam Rasheed Aboumorra, Luana Ladu, Valentina Vavassori, Susanna Albertini, Gabor Mester, Piergiuseppe Morone	Full conference paper (SDEWES 2024 Conference)	Accepted for presentation and published as archival paper	T1.2
Assessing the Impact of Digital Product Passports on the Transition to a Circular Bio-based Economy	Mariam Rasheed Aboumorra, Luana Ladu	Conference paper (Eu-SPRI 2024 Conference)	Abstract accepted; paper in progress	T1.2
Exploring the Potential of Digital Product Passports for establishing a Circular Bio-	Mariam Rasheed Aboumorra, Luana Ladu	Conference paper (EURAS 2024 Conference)	Paper included in EURAS 2024 Proceedings	T1.2

based Economy: the Role of Standardisation				
Insights from an Extensive Multi- step Multi- stakeholder Engagement in Circular Bio- based Economy	Gülşah Yilan, Elina Dace, Mariam Rasheed Aboumorra, Luana Ladu, Valentina Vavassori, Susanna Albertini, Gabor Mester, Piergiuseppe Morone	Open Research Europe	Paper submitted	T1.2
Assessing Barriers to the Circular Bio- Based Economy Through Multi- Criteria Decision- Making: Insights from a combined AHP and ANP Analyses	Paula de la Sen de la Cruz, Laura García Laverde, Gülşah Yilan, Eleonora Staffieri, Mariam Rasheed, Luana Ladu, Andrea Bassi	Open Research Europe	In preparation	T1.3
Engineered wood products for construction based on beech and poplar resources in Europe	Joris Van Acker, Liselotte De Ligne, Tobi Hallez, Jan Van den Bulcke	Conference paper (Hardwood 2024 Conference)	Keynote, Paper draft submitted	T3.3
Building an Inclusive Bioeconomy: Addressing Gender, Age, and Socio- Cultural Barriers for a Just Transition	Gülşah Yilan, Andrea M. Bassi, Edvin Andreasson, Marco Bianchi, Susanna Albertini, Valentina Vavassori, Piergiuseppe Morone	Societal Impacts	Under review (second round)	WP1, WP2, WP4

2.5.2 Case study factsheets

Since the work on the case studies took place in a later stage of the project, #4 initial sector-specific factsheets were developed at M21 to provide preliminary insights. These early factsheets included the name of the sector, its limits, challenges and impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, promising applications (with SUSTRACK case study titles and scores per selection criteria), barriers to the uptake of bio-based solutions, and proposed policy actions. They allowed stakeholders to start engaging with the material while the more detailed work was still ongoing.

Later, at M33, the final #4 case study factsheets were produced, incorporating the final results organised by sector. These documents include a brief description of each sector, a summary of the relevant case studies, and the recommendations identified in the case studies to improve sustainable practices.

All factsheets were published on the project website and disseminated through dedicated social media campaigns, increasing outreach and stakeholder engagement. Their impact can be summarised as 1458 views.

Figure 5 - The covers from the different sectoral and case study factsheets

2.5.3 Conference outcome factsheets

A total of #23 factsheets (KPI: #3) summarizing the main takeaways from the INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences have been created after a thorough analysis of the results, thanks to the proactive collaboration of partners (Figure 6).

All factsheets consistently included the following information:

- Brief introduction of SUSTRACK;
- Objectives and format of the conferences;
- Participant information;
- Main results from the conference.

Due to the complexity of how the IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences were organized, multiple factsheets were produced for these events, overcoming the KPI foreseen.

For IMPLEMENT, a **general factsheet** was created along with #4 **sector-specific factsheets**. For

DEPLOY, a **general factsheet** was accompanied by **#5 country-specific factsheets**, covering the locations where the conferences took place (the Netherlands & Belgium, Italy, Slovakia, Spain, Germany). The general factsheet of the DEPLOY conference, which included the final conclusions on policy instruments and capacity building, was translated into five languages and integrated into the SUSTRACK toolkit (see Section 2.5.5). In addition, each country-specific factsheet was translated into its respective national language (Dutch, Italian, Slovak, Spanish, and German).

These materials were shared on the SUSTRACK website and on social media to maximise dissemination and impact, reaching in total 2452 views (last update: 30/10/2025).

Figure 6 - A page from the different conference outcomes factsheets

2.5.4 Case study videos

#4 case study videos were produced at M33, one for each sector ([chemical](#), [construction](#), [plastics](#), [textile](#)). Each video, of around 2 minutes, was designed in a format suitable also for social media: short, dynamic, and informative. The videos include a brief description of the sector, a presentation of the relevant case studies used to formulate the recommendations, and a concise overview of the recommendations themselves to improve sustainable practices - presented as final results of SUSTRACK’s WP3 research. To ensure accessibility in different contexts, the videos were created using short impactful sentences combined with a sequence of images, allowing them to be effectively used even in noisy environments, as they do not require audio.

The videos were published on the project website and disseminated through social media channels, reaching 19534 views (last update: 30/10/2025).

Figure 7 - Some screenshots from the #4 case study videos

2.5.5 Toolkits

At M36, [a set of 6 modular toolkits](#) targeting the partners' country (IT, NL, SK, DE, BE, ES), was ultimately produced including the **English, Italian, Dutch, Slovak, German, Spanish** versions. The Belgian partner UGENT belongs to the Flemish-speaking region of Belgium, where **Dutch is the official language**; therefore, the **Dutch toolkit** effectively covers both the Netherlands and Belgium. Moreover, as **German is also one of Belgium's official languages**, the **German toolkit** further contributes to ensuring linguistic coverage across the Belgian territory. The toolkits were designed to package Sustrack's outcomes as actionable knowledge, supporting exploitation and uptake by stakeholders while maximising impact and awareness among the main target audiences.

Each toolkit includes:

- The general factsheets stemming from the DEPLOY conferences, which comprises:
 - the final conclusions on policy instruments, both general and sectoral;
 - capacity building materials, provided as a written summary (in all languages).
- Two dedicated webinars held in English to complement the written capacity building materials.
- A synthesis of the main results per Work Package in factsheet and video formats, with links to further resources for deeper exploration (in all languages).

The toolkits were published on the project website and disseminated through social media channels, reaching 273 views (last update: 30/10/2025). The data currently available on downloads and views may be limited and not representative, as the toolkits were only published towards the end of the project.

Funded by the European Union

SUSTRACK

NATIONAL EVENTS

Format: 4 national workshops + 1 national survey

112 external participants in total

Funded by the European Union

SUSTRACK

Policy set: Market-based Instruments

	Biomass/CHG reduction	Circularity/Toxicity
Promoting transition	Innovation subsidy for innovative non-fossil chemicals, including supporting market penetration of novel products	Innovation subsidy for developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to EU-SSbD (Safe and Sustainable by Design) - framework and decontamination technologies
Limit resource use	Carbon tax for fossil feedstocks in chemicals production and for low-value biomass uses	Pollution tax on key Substances of Concern that pose major risks to health or environment and thus inhibit circularity (e.g., lead, PFAS, flame retardants)

INNOVATION SUBSIDY FOR INNOVATIVE NON-FOSSIL CHEMICALS, INCLUDING SUPPORTING MARKET PENETRATION OF NOVEL PRODUCTS

Key opportunities

- Allows integration with existing measures beyond the chemical sector and, if properly designed, prevents overuse of biomass resources (and ensures proper distribution between sectors).
- Complement innovation subsidies with market-based approaches, such as increasing the cost of fossil fuels and subsidizing biogenic fuels, which are seen as priorities for supporting market penetration of novel non-fossil products.

Funded by the European Union

SUSTRACK

Methodology

A comprehensive grey and white literature analysis was carried out for the identification of limits of the linear fossil-based economy, along with the barriers to transitioning to CBBE. Through stakeholder engagement activities, i.e., a focus group, interviews and a survey, we reached a validated set of barriers. A further step of prioritisation was conducted through the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). The AHP analysis was complemented with the Analytical Network Process (ANP) to identify the interdependencies of barriers to clusters.

Country performance analysis

SUSTRACK

Choose the key areas to display results

Click "update" to calculate or update assessment results

Causal Loop Diagram

SUSTRACK

Figure 8 - Some screenshots of the English versions of the factsheets, as well as capacity building videos

2.6 Multimedia

2.6.1 Promotional video

A **Promotional video** of the project was designed and produced in M1, with the aim of explaining in a comprehensible and attractive way the SUSTRACK objectives, target beneficiaries and expected outcomes. Further details on the concept, design and dissemination of the video were already provided in D6.2.

2.6.2 Video teasers for social media campaigns

The first of the two video teasers was designed in the first reporting period and has already been described in detail in D6.2

In the second reporting period, at M36, a video promoting the main results of the project was created to highlight SUSTRACK's key achievements in a concise and engaging way, sparking stakeholders' curiosity and interest. Thanks to its short and dynamic format - combining sentences with images and requiring no audio - the video was particularly suited for social media dissemination. It was used as a teaser across SUSTRACK's channels to increase the visibility of the project results and support their further exploitation.

The video was published on the project website and disseminated through social media channels, reaching 5373 views (last update: 30/10/2025). The data currently available on views may be limited, as the video was only published towards the end of the project.

Figure 9 - Screenshot of the SUSTRACK second video teaser

2.6.3 Promotional banners

Promotional banners played an important role in the digital promotion of SUSTRACK and its activities across social media platforms. These banners serve as visual representations of core messages, capturing attention and conveying them effectively.

#24 promotional banners have been shared on SUSTRACK social media (Figure 10), in order to both promote the project's activities and events, driving interest and participation from diverse

audiences, and to keep the target audience engaged. In particular, the following banners have been produced:

- #3 to promote the DESIGN conference;
- #4 to promote the IMPLEMENT conference;
- #1 to promote the “Beyond SUSTRACK co-creation workshop”;
- #1 to promote the “Projects4Future” mobilization and mutual learning workshop;
- #2 to promote the WP5 survey;
- #5 to promote the DEPLOY conferences;
- #4 to promote newsletters and press releases;
- #3 to celebrate winter and summer breaks (2024, 2025);
- #1 to promote the SUSTRACK final event.

Figure 10 - Some examples of promotional banners shared on SUSTRACK social media (one for each category)

2.6.4 Thematic cards and infographics cards

Thematic cards are designed to convey content in an accessible and engaging way, addressing both general concepts and topics connected to the four specific sectors covered by the project. Their purpose is to inform and educate all target audiences - in particular policymakers, industry representatives and researchers, by presenting key results and insights.

Infographic cards, instead, as originally foreseen in the Grant Agreement, were intended to provide more technical and data-driven information on cross-cutting issues such as life cycle assessment (LCA), monitoring tools for the transition, and socio-economic impacts. However, during the implementation of the project, the consortium decided not to pursue this specific format. Given the nature of the results and the timing of their publication, it was considered more

effective to produce more thematic cards, which proved better suited to communicate the project’s findings.

A first set of #7 thematic cards was created and launched during the first reporting period, and is already described in detail in D6.2. In the second reporting period, a further set of #26 thematic cards was produced and disseminated through social media channels to promote SUSTRACK research (Figure 11). These cards focused first on illustrating the methodology behind the prioritisation of barriers hindering the transition to a Circular Bio-based Economy, and subsequently on presenting the main results of the AHP and ANP analyses carried out in WP1 (further described in Section 2.8.2.2).

Figure 11 - Some examples of the thematic cards produced in the second reporting period

2.7 Dissemination and communication materials

2.7.1 Email campaigns

Email campaigns proved to be a key communication tool within SUSTRACK, enabling direct interaction with stakeholders and encouraging their active participation in project events and activities. Through this approach, SUSTRACK successfully engaged stakeholders across the four sectors (textile, construction, plastics, chemical) and different geographical regions, fostering a sense of involvement and ownership. The campaigns were carefully designed to deliver targeted and relevant information, including updates, invitations, and opportunities for engagement. Consequently, they contributed significantly to building connections, promoting collaboration, and supporting the overall success of SUSTRACK's initiatives.

Thanks to the coordinated effort of all partners, SUSTRACK launched #9 main email campaigns in the second reporting period, focused on the following topics:

- DESIGN conference;
- IMPLEMENT conference;
- DEPLOY conference;
- “Beyond SUSTRACK co-creation workshop”;
- “Projects4Future” mobilisation and mutual learning workshop;
- WP5 Survey;
- Final event;
- Second SUSTRACK newsletter.
- Third SUSTRACK newsletter.

2.7.2 Newsletters

The first newsletter was distributed via email and promoted on 31 October 2023 on the [SUSTRACK website](#) and Social Media platforms ([Twitter X](#) [LinkedIn](#)), reaching 737 stakeholders through the different channels (views on LinkedIn, Twitter X, direct distributions, download from SUSTRACK website - last update 23/04/2024). Further details are already reported in D6.2.

The second newsletter was distributed via email and promoted on 31 October 2024 on the [SUSTRACK website](#) and Social Media platforms ([Twitter X](#), [LinkedIn](#)), reaching 1061 stakeholders through the different channels (views on LinkedIn, Twitter X, direct distributions, download/visits from SUSTRACK website - last update 21/10/2025). The newsletter included:

- SUSTRACK research results on:
 - The identification of the most important and influential barriers to the transition towards a Circular Bio-based Economy through stakeholder engagement;
 - SUSTRACK monitoring tool;
 - 11 case studies;
 - Forecasting the transition to CBBE using the Green Economy Model (GEM);
 - Policy priorities for the transition.
- A summary of the SUSTRACK INSPIRE and DESIGN conferences.

The third and final SUSTRACK newsletter was directly distributed via email to 232 stakeholders and promoted at the end of October on the [SUSTRACK website](#) (23 October) and social media platforms (30 October - [Twitter X](#) and [LinkedIn](#)), reaching in total 304 stakeholders through the different channels (views on LinkedIn, Twitter X, direct distributions, download/visits from

SUSTRACK website - last update 30/10/2025). The data currently available on downloads and views may be limited and not representative, as the newsletter was only published towards the end of the project.

This edition summarised the final results of the project, presenting the main outcomes under five key thematic areas:

- Identifying and Prioritising Barriers to the Circular Bio-based Transition
- Monitoring Progress in the Circular Bio-based Transition
- From Fossil to Bio-based Chains: Case Studies and Policy Pathways for the Circular Bio-based Transition
- Scenarios and Modelling for a Sustainable Bio-based Future
- Policy Options and Roadmaps for the Circular Bio-based Transition

The newsletter also included a summary of SUSTRACK's DEPLOY Conferences, outlining the main outcomes and insights collected from the national policy dialogues. All contents were linked to the different materials included in the SUSTRACK toolkit, with the specific goal of maximising their visibility and encouraging further use by stakeholders and policymakers.

Figure 12 - Screenshots of the first pages of the second and third newsletters

2.7.3 Press releases

A first and a second press releases were distributed during the first reporting period. Further details are already reported in D6.2.

A third press release was distributed and promoted on 31 October 2024 on the [SUSTRACK website](#), Social Media platforms ([Twitter X](#), [LinkedIn](#)), and through partners' Press Offices. The release highlighted SUSTRACK's significant progress in advancing Europe's transition to a circular bio-based economy, summarising key achievements such as the identification and prioritisation of

barriers to the transition, the development of the SUSTRACK Monitoring Tool, the selection and assessment of 11 sector-specific case studies, the use of the Green Economy Model (GEM) to forecast socio-economic and environmental impacts, and the successful INSPIRE and DESIGN conferences that consolidated stakeholder engagement and validated project findings. The third press release reached more than 793 stakeholders, through the different channels (views on LinkedIn, Twitter X, direct distributions, download/visits from SUSTRACK website - last update 21/10/2025).

A fourth and final press release was distributed and promoted at the end of October via the [SUSTRACK website](#) (23 October), social media platforms (30 October - [Twitter X](#) and [LinkedIn](#)), and through partners' press offices. The release focused on promoting the SUSTRACK toolkit, which compiles the project's key outcomes and policy-relevant materials to support the transition towards a circular bio-based economy. The press release provided a concise overview of the project's main achievements, including the identification and prioritisation of barriers to the transition, the development of the SUSTRACK Monitoring Tool, the assessment of sector-specific case studies, the modelling of scenarios for a sustainable bio-based future, and the definition of policy options and roadmaps for systemic change. By highlighting these final results, the release aimed to raise awareness of the toolkit as a practical resource for stakeholders, policymakers, and industry actors committed to accelerating Europe's circular bio-based transition. The final press release reached more than 226 stakeholders, through the different channels (views on LinkedIn, Twitter X, direct distributions, download/visits from SUSTRACK website - last update 30/10/2025). The data currently available on downloads and views may be limited and not representative, as the press release was only published towards the end of the project.

Partners distributed the press releases among their networks.

2.8 Social media

2.8.1 Social media profiles

The official social media pages of the project ([LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter X](#)) were created and launched at M1, together with the website launch, as described in D6.1. SUSTRACK uses these channels as key tools to reach its stakeholders, including research centres and universities, companies, B2B industries, European projects, institutional bodies, and policymakers.

During the second reporting period, an additional channel was leveraged: [YouTube](#), where SUSTRACK uploaded conference recordings, case study videos, and capacity building materials. This channel has proven highly effective in engaging stakeholders, rapidly accumulating a significant number of followers and views, and complementing the professional updates provided through LinkedIn and Twitter X.

Thanks to continuous activity on all channels, SUSTRACK has increased its visibility, publishing over 429 posts/videos in diverse formats (banners, videos, photos, thematic cards) to maximise engagement, and reaching 5489 followers in total (last update 30/10/2025). Social media communication remains focused on frequent and relevant content combined with dialogue, targeting SUSTRACK's primary audience. In particular, SUSTRACK social media channels were animated with a variety of content including project's activities, events and results, insights from deliverables, articles, news. As previously noted in D6.1, the general public is considered a secondary audience, with civil society/citizens and media as secondary targets for dissemination. The KPI related to the number of social media posts was not fully achieved. This was due to a strategic choice to prioritise content directly linked to SUSTRACK's activities and results, rather

than publishing more general news about the circular bioeconomy. The focus was therefore placed on ensuring that all communication outputs were relevant, high-quality, and consistent with the project’s objectives and messaging, rather than on meeting quantitative targets.

The addition of YouTube allows SUSTRACK to further exploit audiovisual content, reinforcing stakeholder engagement and showcasing project results in a highly accessible format.

Table 3 offers a specific overview of the SUSTRACK followers for each social media channel (last update 30/10/2025).

Table 3 -SUSTRACK followers on LinkedIn, Twitter X and YouTube

LinkedIn	
Followers	611
Link	https://www.linkedin.com/company/sustrack/
Twitter X	
Followers	178
Link	https://twitter.com/SUSTRACK_eu
You Tube	
Followers	4700
Link	https://twitter.com/SUSTRACK_eu

Figure 13 - Examples of social media posts

2.8.2 Social media campaigns

During the first reporting period, #2 social media campaigns (“INSPIRE Conference” and “Cluster of barriers” social media campaigns) were launched, described in detail in D6.2. In the second reporting period, further #3 campaigns were carried out and are described in detail below.

2.8.2.1 “DESIGN Conference” social media campaign

The social media campaign for the DESIGN conference was carefully designed to maximise outreach and attract the attention of potentially interested stakeholders from all relevant sectors (chemical, construction, plastics, textile). Its main goal was to encourage registration and active participation in the event, using dedicated carousel/cards (Figure 14), to create visually engaging and informative content.

The campaign provided a brief overview of the case studies involved in each sector. In addition, it clearly communicated the value proposition for different stakeholder groups, explaining what participants could expect from the event and how their input could contribute to shaping

outcomes. By presenting both the content and the participatory opportunities in an accessible and appealing format, the campaign helped generate interest, stimulate dialogue, and strengthen stakeholder engagement prior to the conference.

Figure 14 - A couple of screenshots of the “DESIGN conference” social media campaign

This campaign reached 105 reactions, 55 reposts (*note that data on views are no longer available*) on LinkedIn and 632 views, 26 likes, 10 retweets on Twitter X (last update: 21/20/2025).

2.8.2.2 “Breaking Barriers: Unlocking the Circular Bio-based Economy” social media campaign

In the second reporting period, the “Breaking Barriers: Unlocking the Circular Bio-based Economy” social media campaign (Figure 15) was launched to accompany the release of the #26 thematic cards, representing a direct continuation of the “Cluster of Barriers” campaign launched in the first reporting period (details in D6.2). While the initial campaign served as a teaser, this new campaign aimed to present in detail the barriers hindering the transition to a circular, low-carbon, bio-based economy, which were identified and prioritised through the WP1 work.

The campaign provided a comprehensive overview of the methodology used to reach the final results, including both the AHP and ANP analyses. Then, the campaign presented the results of the AHP analysis, which highlighted the most important clusters of barriers – Economic and Governance – and detailed the main barriers within each cluster (Economic, Governance, Environmental, Technical, Cultural, Structural) that impede the transition towards a circular bio-based economy. The campaign also showcased the outcomes of the ANP analysis, which allowed researchers to identify which barriers within each cluster exert the greatest influence on other clusters, exploring interdependencies and interconnections between barriers to provide a more nuanced understanding of the systemic challenges to the transition.

The objectives of the campaign were multiple:

- To maintain stakeholders engaged on social media and provide them with actionable knowledge;
- To increase stakeholders’ awareness of the methodological rigor and scientific approach behind the identification and prioritisation of barriers, as well as enable them to

understand the key leverage points for supporting the transition to a circular bio-based economy;

- To stimulate dialogue and feedback among stakeholders, encouraging them to interact with the content, share it within their networks, and engage with SUSTRACK’s research outputs.
- To attract new followers to SUSTRACK’s social media channels.

Figure 15 - Some screenshots of the “Breaking Barriers: Unlocking the Circular Bio-based Economy” social media campaign

This campaign reached 3597 views, 162 reactions, 9 repost on LinkedIn and 589 views, 27 likes, 3 retweets on Twitter X (last update: 21/10/2025).

2.8.2.3 “IMPLEMENT Conference” social media campaign

The social media campaign for the IMPLEMENT conference was planned and executed to maximise stakeholder engagement and encourage active participation in the event, also based on the success of the “DESIGN Conference” social media campaign. A variety of dedicated carousel/cards posts were created with the aim of providing clear and compelling information about the conference, including who should attend, why their presence was valuable, and the type of contributions they could bring to the discussions for each sector of interest (chemical, construction, plastics, textile). Each piece of content was designed to communicate the relevance of the event, ensuring that participants understood both the opportunities and the potential benefits of their involvement.

In addition, a series of cards was specifically developed to promote the keynote speakers, highlighting their expertise and professional background. These materials were designed to be visually appealing and easily shareable, encouraging keynote speakers to repost them within their own networks. This strategy not only increased visibility for the conference but also helped create a ripple effect, reaching potential participants who might not have been directly in the project’s communication channels.

By combining informative, engaging, and shareable content, the campaign effectively captured the attention of stakeholders and fostered anticipation and excitement for the conference, strengthened stakeholder engagement prior to the event, and supported the creation of meaningful interactions during the sessions.

Figure 16 - Some screenshots of the “IMPLEMENT conference” social media campaign

This campaign reached 5016 views, 177 reactions, 52 repost on LinkedIn and 563 views, 30 likes, 8 retweets on Twitter X (last update: 21/10/2025).

2.9 Other graphical materials

As the dissemination and communication leader, FVA was also in charge of the graphical design of interactive tools and dissemination materials, including deliverables, presentations, and publications, ensuring consistency with the project’s objectives, brand identity, and stakeholder needs.

For interactive tools used during project events such as the DESIGN, IMPLEMENT, and DEPLOY conferences, screenshots and descriptions are provided in Chapter 4. In general, these tools were carefully designed in close collaboration with partners to integrate research requirements, optimise usability, enhance visual appeal, and maximise stakeholder engagement.

Similarly, dissemination and communication materials were developed to support partners and address specific requests, even if limited in this reporting period. The design of these materials followed key principles:

- **Visual Coherence:** All materials adhered to SUSTRACK’s brand identity guidelines, including consistent use of colours, fonts, and graphical elements.
- **Clarity and Readability:** Graphical components were created to ensure easy comprehension, employing appropriate font sizes, spacing, and contrast for optimal legibility.
- **Visual Impact:** Engaging and eye-catching visuals were incorporated to attract attention and effectively communicate complex information in a clear and accessible way.

Figure 17 - A couple of examples of the graphical materials produced

3 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

In SUSTRACK, various dissemination and communication activities were undertaken through collaborative efforts among all partners. Below (Table 4) is a brief summary of the KPIs foreseen and achieved, while detailed descriptions of individual activities are provided in the subsequent sections.

Table 4 - KPIs foreseen and achieved for dissemination and communication activities (including activities of the first reporting period)

Activity	KPIs	KPI Reached
Talks at events and conferences (live and online)	>10	8 Conferences, 417+ participants 17 Dissemination events in Clustering activities and Collaboration with EU-funded project, 719+ participants
Meetings with stakeholders	>40 participants reached	12 Meetings, 460+ participants
Direct and indirect reach of SUSTRACK primary and secondary target audience	At least 10,000 stakeholders directly and indirectly in total (among them 500 primary targets reached indirectly through communication and dissemination activities)	3 Education and training lectures, 430 participants 7 Events and Exhibitions, 1845+ participants Newsletters, 600 recipients Social Media, >19000 followers reached (also through partners' channels)

Other activities involving actively the stakeholders (primary target audience), such as capacity building and co-creation exercises are reported in Chapter 4. Those activities are pivotal not only for stakeholder engagement, but also for strengthening the dissemination and communication of the project's results.

3.1 Dissemination activities

SUSTRACK partners performed several dissemination activities during the last 18 months of the project, by participating as speakers in various conferences and workshops, by providing education and training to universities, but also by collaborating with other EU-funded projects and initiatives. Meetings with stakeholders were also organised in order to present SUSTRACK results.

The following sections describe the dissemination activities undertaken to reach the different target stakeholders.

3.1.1 Conferences

SUSTRACK partners participated into 6 conferences to present SUSTRACK results. Further details are reported in Table 5.

Table 5 - SUSTRACK Dissemination activities: conferences

Partner(s)	Dissemination activity description	Target audience	Impact
UNITELMA, BAM	17/05/2024: Presentation of first SUSTRACK outputs under the UNITELMA Bioeconomy Day activities (Rome and online)	Research communities International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.) EU Institutions Regional authorities Local authorities Civil society Citizens	80 participants
UNITELMA	11/09/24: UNITELMA represented SUSTRACK at the 19th Conference on Sustainable Development of Energy, Water, and Environment Systems (SDEWES), delivering a well-received presentation on “Mapping the barriers to a sustainable transition: insights from an extensive grey literature analysis and focus group discussion”.	Research communities	N.D.
UNITELMA	28/03/2025: SUSTRACK WP1 work presented in the context of the b-Act symposium.	Research communities Industry, business partners	87 participants
UNITELMA	09/04/2025: A conference paper was presented on the gender, age, and socio-cultural factors in the bioeconomy at the “EU-Gender Circular Bioeconomy	Research communities	30 participants

	Innovation in the EU” in Ferrara, Italy.		
UNITELMA	04/06/2025: Some outputs from WP1 and WP2 were presented at the ExeBio International Congress in Reims, France.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research communities Industry, business partners National authorities Regional authorities Civil society 	150 participants
WR	11/06/2025: Results of the WP3 case study on methanol from waste were presented at the European Biomass Conference & Exhibition (EUBCE), 2025, in Valencia. The presentation was titled “Towards circular biobased chemicals: unlocking the potential of the waste-to-methanol value chain”.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research communities Industry National authorities Regional authorities Civil society 	50+ participants

Figure 18 - Pictures from conferences

3.1.2 Meetings

SUSTRACK partners participated in meetings to disseminate SUSTRACK results. Further details are reported in Table 6.

Table 6 - SUSTRACK Dissemination activities: meetings

Partner(s)	Dissemination activity description	Target audience	Impact
UNITELMA	04/10/2024: Presentation of the SUSTRACK publication entitled “Barriers to transitioning to a circular bio-based economy: Findings from an industrial perspective” at the Cooperation, development and cross-border transfer of Industrial Symbiosis among industry and stakeholders; Unlocking the power of Industrial Symbiosis with LIAISE. The event	Research communities Industry, business partners	30 participants

	was hybrid (online and onsite in Riga, Latvia)		
UGENT	23/10/2024: 27th IPC Session in Bordeaux. Presentation on combining poplar with other wood species for engineered wood products, highlighting the potential of wood-based resources to produce high-quality materials, enhance circularity, and promote the use of bio-based alternatives.	<p>Research communities</p> <p>Industry</p> <p>Innovators</p> <p>Investors</p> <p>EU & International institutions</p> <p>Other EU-funded projects and initiatives</p>	N.D.
UNITELMA, FVA	<p>20/05/2025: SUSTRACK joined Aperibio, a networking event dedicated to fostering new ideas and collaborations in the field of bioeconomy, held at Spazio Europa in Rome.</p> <p>Organised by APRE, in collaboration with Università degli Studi di Roma UnitelmaSapienza and the EC Representation in Italy, Aperibio brought together experts, researchers, and innovators to explore the future of a sustainable, circular bio-based Europe.</p> <p>SUSTRACK actively participated in the co-creation session, sharing key results and insights from its work, as well as communicating the tools and knowledge we are developing to support evidence-based policymaking. The project materials were also presented, including the official roll-up.</p>	<p>Research communities</p> <p>Industry, business partners</p> <p>Innovators</p> <p>Investors</p> <p>EU institutions</p> <p>Other EU-funded projects and initiatives</p>	100 participants
DBFZ	Information round for the whole DBFZ regarding current projects and key results. - The results about the material use sectors scenarios (WP4) were presented.	Research community	60 participants

DBFZ	Internal information round for the research area systemic contribution of biomass. The results from the SUSTRACK Tools (monitoring dashboard, GEM model) as well as policy factsheets were presented.	Research community	30 participants
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Figure 19 - Pictures from meetings

3.1.3 Dissemination activities in Clustering activities and Collaboration with EU-funded projects

SUSTRACK partners disseminated several SUSTRACK results in the context of clustering activities and collaboration with other EU-Funded projects and initiatives (Figure 20). Further details are reported in Table 7.

Table 7 - SUSTRACK Dissemination activities in Clustering activities and Collaboration with EU-funded projects

Partner(s)	Dissemination activity description	Target audience	Impact
UNITELMA	07/06/2024: Gülşah Yılan presented groundbreaking insights from SUSTRACK at the 3-CO “Pathways to Smart Certification of Bio-Based Systems” webinar. The focus was on defining a circular bio-based economy and identifying	Research communities Industry, business partners Other EU-funded projects and initiatives	50 participants

	the barriers hindering the transition towards sustainable future.		
FVA	26/06/2024: SUSTRACK flyers and project video were distributed/projected at BIOTRANSFORM booth in the context of EUBCE 2024.	<p>Research communities</p> <p>Industry, business partners</p> <p>Innovators</p> <p>Investors</p> <p>Other EU-funded projects and initiatives</p>	N.D.
WR	27/06/2024: WR representative was invited as panelist in the roundtable “Obstacles and opportunities for biomass resources mobilization for the circular bioeconomy” organised by BIOTRANSFORM with sister projects in the context of EUBCE 2024.	<p>Research communities</p> <p>Industry, business partners</p> <p>Other EU-funded projects and initiatives</p>	30 participants
PEDAL, TECNALIA, DBFZ	09/10/2024: SUSTRACK presented its monitoring tool at “ROBIN 1 st MML” in Stuttgart and online	<p>Research communities</p> <p>Other EU-funded projects and initiatives</p>	20 on-site participants
FVA	15-17/10/2024: SUSTRACK slides about project results shared during ECOSYSTEX conference 2024	<p>Research communities</p> <p>Industry, business partners</p> <p>Innovators</p> <p>Investors</p> <p>EU institutions</p> <p>Other EU-funded projects and initiatives</p>	120 participants
BAM	13/03/2025: SUSTRACK presented its results at the BIOTRANSFORM final event.	<p>Research communities</p> <p>Industry, business partners</p>	70 participants

		<p>Innovators</p> <p>Investors</p> <p>EU institutions</p> <p>Other EU-funded projects and initiatives</p>	
FVA	<p>13/05/2025: presentation of consolidated outcomes from the 2nd Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshop “Projects4Future” (see Section 5.2.1) at the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster Final Event in Brussels</p>	<p>Research communities</p> <p>Industry, business partners</p> <p>Innovators</p> <p>Investors</p> <p>EU institutions</p> <p>Other EU-funded projects and initiatives</p>	N.D.
UNITELMA	<p>19/09/2025: SUSTRACK final results in the textile sector presented at ECOSYSTECH Insights Series #16 webinar</p>	<p>Research communities</p> <p>Other EU-funded projects and initiatives</p>	66 participants

Figure 20 - Pictures from different clustering activities and collaborations with EU-funded projects

3.1.4 Education and Training events

FVA partner organised 1 education and training event, disseminating Sustrack results to PhD students in academic context. Further details are reported in Table 8.

Table 8 - Sustrack Dissemination activities: Education and Training events

Partner(s)	Dissemination activity description	Target audience	Impact
FVA	22/05/2024: Presentation of Sustrack to 20 PhD Students of Università Vita-Salute San Raffaele (Milan), in the context of a “Career Day”	Citizens	20 on-site participants

3.2 Communication activities

Sustrack partners performed several communication activities during the last 18 months of the project, by organising and participating in one large scale event, but also promoting the project online (e.g., via social media, websites, newsletters).

The following sections describe the communication activities undertaken to reach the different target stakeholders.

3.2.1 Event and Exhibition

SUSTRACK partners participated in one large scale event to communicate about the project, its activities and related topics (Figure 21). Further details are reported in Table 9.

Table 9 - SUSTRACK Communication activities: Events and Exhibitions

Partner(s)	Communication activity description	Target audience	Impact
FVA	27-28/09/2024: European Researchers' Night, in Frascati, Rome, Italy. The FVA New Media Research team engaged citizens in collaboration with GenB and BlueMissionMed projects, conducting a fun quiz about sustainability and the "Escape4Future - Chemistry meets Circular Bioeconomy" game, that educates by playing key facts about the bioeconomy and environmental protection. The experience was tailored for two different types of players: a simplified version of the game for the younger ones, and a more challenging gameplay for the teen-agers and young adults.	Citizens	350+ citizens directly engaged

Figure 21 - Live pictures from events and exhibitions

3.2.2 Promotion of SUSTRACK in external Newsletters

SUSTRACK project and its activities were promoted in 5 external newsletters. Further details are reported in Table 10.

Table 10 - SUSTRACK Communication activities: Newsletters

Partner(s)	Communication activity description	Target audience	Impact
PEDAL	14/10/2024: Online Article in Circular Slovakia's newsletter about the DESIGN conference closing event. 01/12/2024: Online Article in Circular Slovakia's newsletter about publication of SUSTRACK's deliverables.	Industry, business partners Civil society Specific user communities	Not measured

	<p>01/02/2025: OnlineArticle in Circular Slovakia's newsletter promoting IMPLEMENT workshops series and IMPLEMENT conference.</p> <p>09/06/2025: Promotion of Slovak DEPLOY conference by Slovak Bioeconomy Cluster, through email to its members</p> <p>01/08/2025: Promotion of DEPLOY Conference results in Circular Slovakia Newsletter</p>		
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3.2.3 Promotion of SUSTRACK in partners' and other Social Media

SUSTRACK project and its activities were promoted in partners' social media, which reposted and diffused several contents published by the official project's channels. Notably, SUSTRACK contents were also promoted/diffused by other social media channels (e.g., ECOSYSTEX, invited keynote speakers to the SUSTRACK conferences). All details are reported in Table 11.

Table 11 - SUSTRACK Communication activities: Social Media

Partner(s)	Communication activity description	Target audience	Impact
UNITELMA, FVA, PEDAL, TECNALIA, CIRCE, KE, UNIFE, WR	Partners, reposted several contents published by SUSTRACK project, during the overall duration of the last 18 months.	All target audience	<p>UNITELMA and personal profiles 3000 followers</p> <p>FVA, EuBioNet and personal profiles 1000 followers</p> <p>PEDAL 1489 followers</p> <p>TECNALIA 839 followers</p> <p>CIRCE 1500 followers</p> <p>KE and personal profiles 500 followers</p>

			UNIFE 1707 followers UGENT 954 followers DBFZ 5385 followers
FVA	Promotion of SUSTRACK events and videos on ECOSYSTEMEX social media, during the overall duration of the last 18 months.	Primary target audiences	Not measured (total followers: 3604)
FVA	Promotion of SUSTRACK events in third-parties' social media (e.g., SUSTRACK conferences keynote speakers etc.), during the overall duration of the last 18 months.	Primary target audiences	Not measured

3.2.4 Promotion of SUSTRACK in partners' and other website

SUSTRACK project was promoted in several partners' and external websites. Details are reported in Table 12.

Table 12 - SUSTRACK Communication activities: Websites

Partner(s)	Communication activity description	Target audience	Impact
FVA	Dedicated website section about project information	Specific user communities	419 visitors (last update: 21/10/2025)
PEDAL	Website article on ISC3's website promoting the IMPLEMENT chemical workshop. Website article on the national DEPLOY workshop findings.	Specific user communities Civil society	N.D.
FVA	Promotion of several SUSTRACK events through ECOSYSTEMEX online calendar .	Specific user communities	N.D.

FVA	Promotion of SUSTRACK deliverables on the ECOSYSTEMEX website .	Specific user communities	N.D.
CIRCE	Dedicated website section about project information	Specific user communities	N.D.

4 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES

Stakeholder engagement has been a central pillar of the SUSTRACK project, ensuring that results were co-created, validated, and effectively communicated to relevant target audiences. Throughout the project, stakeholders from policy, industry, academia, and civil society were actively involved across all WPs to ensure that multiple perspectives informed the project's analyses and policy recommendations.

Engagement activities included a series of events, workshops, surveys and bilateral consultations designed to collect feedback, validate interim findings, and enhance policy relevance. These interactions fostered an open exchange of knowledge and strengthened links with EU and national-level initiatives supporting the transition towards a sustainable and circular economy.

By the end of the project, SUSTRACK had built a diverse stakeholder network and an updated contact database, ensuring balanced representation across sectors and regions. The insights gathered from this network have been instrumental in shaping the project's final outputs and ensuring the uptake and sustainability of its results beyond the project's lifetime.

4.1 Continuous identification and involvement of the SUSTRACK project stakeholders

Stakeholder identification and engagement have been at the core of SUSTRACK's approach to ensuring that project outcomes are robust, inclusive, and relevant to real-world needs. Building on the recruitment strategies outlined in D6.1, stakeholder mapping and engagement activities have been continuously refined and expanded throughout the project to support effective dialogue and collaboration across all WPs.

A variety of targeted strategies were implemented to identify, recruit, and maintain active stakeholder participation (Table 13):

- Direct invitations to relevant stakeholders identified through partners' recommendations and desk research, which included the mapping of related documents, initiatives, associations, projects, and networks. This method built the foundation of the SUSTRACK stakeholder database and proved highly effective, **reaching 447 stakeholders**.
- Re-engagement of survey participants who were invited to contribute to subsequent SUSTRACK consultations (**31 stakeholders reached**).
- Follow-up with online subscribers and form respondents, including individuals and organisations that expressed interest through the SUSTRACK website or event registration forms (**232 stakeholders reached**).
- Collaboration with related projects and initiatives to coordinate stakeholder activities and cross-promote events (**detailed in Chapter 5**). Although not directly quantified, these synergies substantially expanded SUSTRACK's reach and visibility.
- Utilisation of partner networks, notably the European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet) and Circular Slovakia, to disseminate calls for interest and promote participation opportunities across the broader bioeconomy community.
- Communication through newsletters, and social media, distributed widely via partners' channels, keeping stakeholders informed and engaged with SUSTRACK's progress and results, as well as outreach via the project website and social media, overall reaching an **estimated 19000+** individuals, contributing to broader awareness and engagement.

Table 13 - Targeted strategies implemented to identify, recruit, and maintain active stakeholder participation

Engagement Method	Description	Stakeholders Reached	Remarks / Outcomes
Direct invitations (desk research & partner inputs)	Identification through partners' networks, mapping of related initiatives, associations, and projects.	447	Main recruitment channel; formed the backbone of the stakeholder database.
Engagement of survey respondents	Re-engagement of participants from earlier surveys for workshops and consultations.	31	Strengthened continuity and stakeholder ownership of results.
Online forms and expressions of interest	Stakeholders who actively subscribed or showed interest via project forms.	232	Demonstrates spontaneous interest in SUSTRACK topics.
Collaboration with related projects and initiatives	Joint promotion and participation through cross-project activities.	Not measured directly	Enhanced visibility and policy alignment; details in Chapter 5.
Partner networks (e.g., EuBioNet and Circular Slovakia)	Mobilisation of partners' communities via targeted calls and newsletters.	Not measured directly	Expanded reach to bioeconomy stakeholders and EU-level audiences.
Press releases and newsletters	Regular communication updates distributed through partners' channels.	Not measured directly	Maintained continuous engagement and visibility.
Website and social media outreach	Posts, news, and event announcements shared through SUSTRACK and partner platforms.	19000+ (estimated reach)	Supported wide dissemination and awareness-raising.

Overall, SUSTRACK successfully built and maintained a diverse and dynamic stakeholder community, encompassing policy makers, industry representatives, researchers, civil society actors, and other EU-funded initiatives. This network has played a vital role in validating project outcomes, enriching policy discussions, and ensuring that SUSTRACK's legacy continues beyond the project's duration.

4.2 SUSTRACK advisory board

The establishment of the SUSTRACK Advisory Board (AB) has been a cornerstone of the project’s stakeholder engagement strategy. The AB served as the central hub connecting contributors, multipliers, and adopters, providing strategic guidance and acting as a bridge between SUSTRACK and broader stakeholder communities.

Composed of #7 distinguished members representing academia, policy, and industry, the Advisory Board has supported the project throughout its duration. Members contributed their expertise to advise on dissemination strategies and ensure the alignment of SUSTRACK’s results with ongoing policy and research developments in the field of sustainable and circular transitions.

Beyond their advisory role, the AB members have amplified SUSTRACK’s visibility by sharing project findings through their professional networks, participating in key dissemination events, and contributing to online events organised within the project framework. Their continuous involvement has strengthened the project’s outreach, credibility, and overall impact, ensuring that SUSTRACK’s messages resonate across relevant EU and international communities.

4.3 Overall details of SUSTRACK stakeholder engagement activities

Table 14 provides a comprehensive overview of all stakeholder engagement activities carried out within SUSTRACK. It presents the timelines, intended outcomes, and the specific stakeholder groups targeted by each activity. In addition, the table includes key performance indicators (KPIs) used to measure the effectiveness of engagement actions. The final column confirms the level of achievement and verifies the fulfilment of the defined KPIs.

Table 14 - SUSTRACK Stakeholder engagement activities

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
Co-creation focus group (T1.2.1), M8	To validate the limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy identified in T1.1	Quadruple Helix (policymakers, businesses, Research and innovation community, NGOs, citizens, etc.)	15 stakeholders	25 stakeholders

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
T1.2.2: Interviews in English and partner's languages, M8>M13	To complement focus group results	Quadruple Helix (policymakers, businesses, Research and innovation community, NGOs, citizens, etc.)	20 interviews with experts (from at least 10 Member States)	21 interviews conducted, engaging 7 European organisations, 1 international organisation and 6 countries
T1.2.2: Survey, M11	To complement focus group results. The results will be shared during the INSPIRE conference (M12).	European and national policy makers, industry professionals, Research and innovation community, NGOs and citizens	Sent to 400 stakeholders in at least 10 Member States, target at least 50 answers (D1.2, M15)	Sent to 396, 55 responses collected, from more than 10 Member States
T1.3: Online workshops/meetings, M13>M15	To prioritise identified limits, to produce preliminary guidelines and policy recommendations	European and national policy makers, industry professionals, Research and innovation community, NGOs and citizens	At least 15 participants across the EU (D1.3, M18)	20 participants with diverse background
WP2-WP5: Co-creation workshops per each of the 4 working groups, M1>36	To co-create case studies of relevance for the circular bio-economy	4 sectors stakeholders working groups (a) the construction sector; (b) the	3 co-creation workshops per each of the 4 working	3 co-creation workshops per each of the 4 working

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
		textile sector; (c) the (fine) chemical sector; and (d) the plastic sector	groups (> 250 participants across 12 workshops) in the context of the INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT conferences	groups (378 participants across 12 workshops)
T3.4: Thematic webinars, M23>30	To transfer knowledge (conclusions and recommendations for the four bio-based sectors)	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	4 thematic webinars (> 100 participants , 200 views; D3.4, M30)	8 sectoral workshop videos (recorded) + 4 case study videos + 1 final video teaser (>300 participants , 25191 views - last update: 30/10/2025)
T4.2: Capacity building activities (materials, model tutorials and online webinars), M20>M23	To transfer knowledge and support further applications of the model	Policy makers and authorities, Policy advisors, NGOs/CSOs, Industrial advisors, Industrial associations/clusters, Research and innovation community	At least 4 online webinars (1 for each sector) involving at least 20 stakeholders each, tot 80; D4.3, M32)	#5 online webinars in the context of the DEPLOY workshops (total of 112 participants , from the 4 sectors). #2 capacity building videos and #1 multilingual

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
				DEPLOY factsheet.
T5.1: Policy co-creation workshop, with 4 sectors stakeholders workgroups in the context of the INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences through plenary and parallel sessions, M10>M28, M30>M34	To validate derived policy priorities and examples of good policies involving the stakeholders involved in the 4 sectors and the case studies	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40) (D5.3, M32)	47 participants at the INSPIRE conference 179 participants on DESIGN workshop series (4 workshops) 158 participants on IMPLEMENT workshop series (4 workshops) 112 participants on DEPLOY workshops

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
T5.1: Prioritisation survey, M33>M34	To provide additional validation to policy priorities and examples of good policies	NGOs/CSOs, Industrial advisors, Industrial associations/clusters, Research and innovation community	Sent to at least 300 stakeholders from at least 10 Member States, target at least 30 answers. (D5.1, D5.2, M18, M34)	Directly sent to 163 stakeholders, and indirectly to 759 through social media, 31 responses received.
T5.2: Capacity building for local stakeholders in the context of the DEPLOY conference, M30>M34	To empower local stakeholders through at least one capacity building seminar, to analyse the implementation of the potential transition paths, based on their contextual specificities (e.g., geographical, social, cultural).	Policy makers, industry professionals, sustainability, Research and innovation community, system community at national and regional levels in the 6 partner's countries	At least 10 stakeholders per each country (6 countries, total 60 participants ; D5.3, D5.4, M32, M33)	112 participants on DEPLOY workshops
T5.3: 6 policy roundtable, M30>M34	To have discussions in the partners' respective countries (country partners)	Policy makers, industry professionals, Research and innovation community, sustainability system community at national and regional levels in the 6	At least 30 participants in each of 6 countries (180 in total; D5.5, M36)	112 participants on DEPLOY workshops. The KPI was not reached due to changes in the organisation of the local events (Belgium

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
		partner's countries		and the Netherlands organised a joint workshop, while Spain replaced the event with a survey directed to key stakeholders).
T6.2: 3 European conferences (i.e., INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT), M1>36	To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions	Policy makers, industry professionals, Research and innovation community, sustainability system community; D6.1, D6.2, D6.3	At least 250 participants	590 participants in total. 87 conference participants in the INSPIRE conference 302 conference participants in the DESIGN conference 201 conference participants in the DESIGN conference

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
INSPIRE Conference (Resp: PC+FVA) M12	Conference (T6.2): To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions and facilitate the adoption, replication and exploitation of SUSTRACK results	EU level: Primary targets	> 100 (EU level)	87 participants
	Co-creation workshop (resp. UNIT+ TECNALIA) - WP3 - MS10: To discuss the case studies	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40)	41 participants
	Policy scenario workshop (T4.1 and T5.1): To verify scenarios developed in T4.1 and contribute to T5.1	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40)	47 participants

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
DESIGN Conference M20 Conference (Resp: PC+FVA)	Conference (T6.2): To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions	EU level: Primary targets	> 50 (EU level)	123 participants on the closing event
	Co-creation workshop (resp BAM+KE) - WP3 - MS10: To discuss the case studies and to define policy priorities and actions across different political levels and policy domains for the sustainable transition, in light of the results of WP3 and WP4; improving the tools and methods of WP2 and WP4	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40)	179 participants on the workshops
IMPLEMENT Conference M28 (Resp: PC+FVA)	Conference (T6.2): To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions and facilitate the adoption, replication and exploitation of SUSTRACK results	EU level: All target audiences	> 100 (EU level)	43 participants on the closing event

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
	Co-creation workshop (resp DBFZ+CIRCE) - T5.3, MS10: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To identify the necessary conditions for the proposed transition pathways; • To prioritise short-, mid- and long-term actions; • To validate policy recommendations (T5.3) 	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40)	158 participants on the workshops
T6.2: 6 national conferences (i.e., DEPLOY)*, M1>36 (Resp: country partners: Italy-UNIT/FVA; Spain-TECNALIA/CIRCE; Germany-BAM/DBFZ; Slovakia-PC; Netherlands-WR; Belgium-UGENT)	Conferences (T6.2): To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by the SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions	National level: All target audiences	At least 180 participants	112 participants on DEPLOY workshops. The KPI was not reached due to changes in the organisation of the local events (Belgium and the Netherlands organised a joint workshop, while Spain replaced the event with a survey directed to key stakeholders).
	6 Policy roundtable discussions in the partners' respective countries (country partners) - T5.3, MS11: To present the revised policy recommendations and guidelines, and ensure that the recommendations and guidelines (both sector- and country specific) are taken up in future policy development	Selected regional and national policy makers specific) are taken up in future policy development	30 participants in each of 6 countries (180 in total)	

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities and month	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	KPI Reached
Final Event (Resp: FVA); M36; Final event - MS12	To present the SUSTRACK outcomes	EC and All target audiences	At least 50 participants	52 external participants , 77 in total

4.4 Thematic webinars

The four thematic webinars initially foreseen were not organised as standalone events. Instead, SUSTRACK decided to make available the **recordings of the sectoral workshops** held during the **DESIGN and IMPLEMENT conferences**, which were uploaded to the project's YouTube channel. This approach ensured the fulfilment of the original objective – to **transfer knowledge and disseminate conclusions and policy recommendations** for the four bio-based sectors (construction, textile, chemical, and plastics). These materials were further complemented by the production of the **sector-specific case study videos** (see Section 2.5.4) and the **final video teaser** summarising SUSTRACK's main results (see Section 2.6.2), thus reinforcing the project's communication and knowledge-sharing efforts.

4.5 Capacity building activities

SUSTRACK developed and delivered a set of resources aimed at transferring knowledge and supporting the further application of the project's models and tools. The capacity-building materials included both video tutorials and written materials. The videos provided step-by-step guidance on how to use the SUSTRACK Monitoring Tool, apply Systems Thinking and Causal Loop Diagrams, and understand the Green Economy Model (GEM). These tutorials were designed to be practical and accessible to a wide audience, enabling stakeholders to independently explore and apply the project's methodologies, as well as understanding the value proposition for them.

The written materials were integrated into the general DEPLOY factsheet, available in all national languages. At national level, capacity-building webinars were organised as an integral part of the DEPLOY conferences (112 participants), during which the same tutorials were presented in the respective national languages. The English versions of tutorial videos were later published on SUSTRACK's official channels, ensuring wider accessibility and long-term usability of the materials beyond the project's lifetime.

4.6 Survey

A survey aimed to prioritise policy instruments that support the transition towards a circular and bio-based economy in four key sectors. Given the complexity of this transition, the survey focused on two main policy approaches: Approach A - Boosting Circularity and Approach B - Ensuring Sustainability of Biomass Use. Each approach included a set of policy instruments representing different types of interventions, from direct regulatory measures to market-based mechanisms.

Respondents were asked to rate each policy instrument on a scale from “fully recommend” to “not recommend at all”, and to select the overall approach they believed would most effectively accelerate the transition in their respective sectors. The survey was directly sent to 163 stakeholders, and indirectly to 759 through social media, and collected **responses from 31 stakeholders** representing a wide range of organisations. The majority of respondents (61%) came from business and industry, reflecting strong engagement from the private sector. This was followed by research and academia (26%), with smaller representation from NGOs and other actors. The composition of respondents ensured that the results captured both scientific insights and practical market perspectives, strengthening the relevance and applicability of the findings for policy development.

In addition, an unforeseen survey was conducted in Spain as an alternative to the originally planned national DEPLOY conference (see Section 4.10), which could not be held due to low confirmed participation. To address this challenge and still meet the objectives of stakeholder engagement, the partners opted for a targeted online survey directed at **9 key Spanish stakeholders** in the textile and plastics sectors. This format offered greater flexibility, allowing participants to respond at their convenience and guaranteeing the collection of valuable feedback on the policy instruments identified within WP5, ensuring the representativeness and usefulness of the Spanish national contribution.

4.7 Online workshops/meetings with stakeholders

A total of **12 meetings and workshops, involving 460+ stakeholders**, were held throughout the entire duration of SUSTRACK. These meetings are described in detail in Chapter 3 (for the second reporting period) and in D6.2.

4.8 DESIGN Conference

Overall Structure and Main Objectives

Between July and September 2024, SUSTRACK organised the “Pathway to DESIGN the Circular Bio-Based Transition” series of co-creation workshops and a concluding conference. The main objectives of these events were threefold. First, they aimed to provide a comprehensive overview of the SUSTRACK value chains—chemical, construction, textiles, and plastics—by presenting detailed process descriptions, market insights, and relevant policy instruments as the basis for discussion. Second, the workshops sought to inspire participants through real-world case studies shared by sector experts, highlighting good practices as well as challenges and barriers in advancing the circular bio-based transition. Finally, they served as a forum for policy dialogue, enabling participants to co-create recommendations addressing environmental, societal, and economic aspects of the transition.

The workshop series comprised four sector-specific co-creation workshops, each focusing on one of the targeted value chains. SUSTRACK experts presented sectoral case studies, while 179 stakeholders contributed through 20 inspirational pitches and interactive discussions using MIRO Boards to capture insights, challenges, and recommendations. The closing DESIGN Conference, attended by 123 experts, synthesised the outcomes of the workshops and translated them into policy recommendations for both industrial and political stakeholders, contributing to a more coordinated and informed transition pathway.

The chosen split format (Figure 22)—a series of shorter, focused workshops followed by a plenary event—was deliberately designed to foster engagement and participation while avoiding the

fatigue associated with lengthy online meetings, as observed during the earlier INSPIRE conference.

Figure 22 - DESIGN conference format

In total, 302 participants took part in the workshops and final event, representing the quadruple helix of innovation—research, industry, policy, and civil society. This diverse participation ensured balanced perspectives and enriched the discussions across the four value chains. PowerPoint presentations and interactive tools such as MIRO Boards and Mentimeter were used to structure dialogue, collect feedback, and present key findings effectively.

Figure 23 - Some screenshots from the DESIGN workshops

Closing Event

Building on the contributions of over 179 stakeholders and 20 case studies from the workshop series, the closing DESIGN Conference presented a synthesis of main findings, including key challenges, good practices, and recommendations across policy, environmental, social, and economic dimensions. This consolidated knowledge base provided insights into sector-specific barriers and opportunities, supporting future actions and policy development.

The event also showcased SUSTRACK's methodologies and tools for monitoring the circular bio-based transition, with particular emphasis on the GEM model, which enables scenario-based analysis of trends and interventions. The conference highlighted SUSTRACK's contribution to EU-level bioeconomy policy, ensuring alignment with ongoing European initiatives.

Organised as an interactive event, the conference encouraged open dialogue and feedback from diverse stakeholders, helping to refine project tools and outputs. Its main outcomes were to deliver actionable knowledge, integrate stakeholder perspectives, and develop policy recommendations to inform future bioeconomy strategies.

Detailed results of the both sectoral workshops and the closing event are accessible on the [SUSTRACK website in the form of factsheets](#). Also, [recordings of the events](#) are available on the SUSTRACK YouTube channel.

Main Takeaways

Learning from the previous INSPIRE Conference, the DESIGN phase adopted a more focused format with four thematic workshops and a final plenary event. This approach improved engagement,

maintained attention, and allowed deeper discussion on sector-specific issues in chemicals, construction, textiles, and plastics.

Participation was broader and more effective, combining expert-level sessions with open plenaries. The use of MIRO and Mentimeter supported interaction and structured feedback, producing relevant, actionable results.

Overall, the DESIGN Conference demonstrated the value of shorter, targeted, and interactive sessions, which led to a richer exchange of ideas and more concrete, policy-relevant recommendations for advancing the circular bio-based transition in Europe.

4.9 IMPLEMENT Conference

Overall Structure and Main Objectives

Between February and March 2025, SUSTRACK organised the “From Vision to Implementation: Shaping Policies to Boost the Circular Bio-Based Transition” series of workshops and a concluding conference. Building on the format of the DESIGN phase, these events aimed to explore how identified policy options could be implemented to accelerate the circular bio-based transition in the chemical, textiles, plastics, and construction sectors.

Figure 24 - IMPLEMENT conference format

The workshops opened with keynote speakers who outlined sectoral challenges, policy trends, and future visions, followed by presentations from SUSTRACK partners detailing the project’s methodology for identifying and assessing policy options. Participants then engaged in interactive discussions using MIRO Boards, evaluating the proposed policies, sharing insights, and suggesting alternative approaches to support a more sustainable and circular economy.

Each workshop fostered dialogue with stakeholders from carbon-intensive sectors, promoting a co-creation process grounded in sector-specific realities. The closing IMPLEMENT Conference, held online on 21 March 2025, synthesised the main takeaways from the workshops, presented

SUSTRACK’s monitoring tools and methods, and highlighted key findings from 11 case studies across the four sectors. These outcomes contributed directly to the formulation of actionable policy recommendations for policymakers and industry stakeholders, reinforcing the project’s aim to move from vision to implementation.

The events primarily targeted policy experts and sectoral stakeholders, with participation from policymakers, researchers, industry representatives, and civil society. In total, 201 participants took part in the workshops and final conference. Interactive tools such as MIRO Boards and PowerPoint presentations supported engagement, helping to collect structured feedback and visualise ideas effectively throughout the sessions.

Closing Event

The closing event of the “From Vision to Implementation: Shaping Policies to Boost the Circular Bio-Based Transition” series marked a key milestone in translating SUSTRACK’s co-created visions into actionable policy options for the textile, construction, plastics, and chemical sectors. It brought together policymakers, industry experts, researchers, and civil society to validate and refine measures supporting the circular bio-based transition.

Building on the IMPLEMENT workshops, the event focused on assessing the policy options developed by SUSTRACK, exploring their strengths, weaknesses, and practical applicability. Participants also reviewed the project’s monitoring tools and methodologies, including the GEM model, and examined findings from 11 case studies that provided evidence-based insights into sectoral challenges and opportunities.

The main goals were to synthesise workshop results, showcase tools supporting policy development, and deliver a set of policy options capable of guiding implementation at both EU and national levels.

Figure 25 - Some screenshots from the IMPLEMENT conference

Detailed results of the both sectoral workshops and the closing event are accessible on the [SUSTRACK website in the form of factsheets](#). Also, [recordings of the events](#) are available on the SUSTRACK YouTube channel.

Main Takeaways

Following the format of the DESIGN phase, the IMPLEMENT Conference combined targeted workshops with a closing event, leading to smoother facilitation and stronger outputs. With increased experience, the consortium ensured more structured sessions and consistent moderation, resulting in a coherent set of policy recommendations supported by case study evidence.

The format proved effective in balancing inclusiveness and depth—plenary sessions engaged wider audiences, while expert discussions captured technical insights. Interactive tools such as the MIRO Board enhanced participation and feedback. Overall, the IMPLEMENT phase confirmed the effectiveness and maturity of SUSTRACK’s engagement model, producing concrete and policy-relevant outcomes to support Europe’s circular bio-based transition.

4.10 DEPLOY Workshops

Between May and August 2025, SUSTRACK organised a series of 4 DEPLOY Workshops across Europe—in Germany, Italy, the Netherlands-Belgium (as online workshops), and Slovakia (as in person workshop)—as the final stage of the project’s participatory process. These events, titled “Planting the Seeds of Systemic Change,” were designed to validate and contextualise the policy options developed during the IMPLEMENT phase, ensuring their relevance to national and sectoral realities. Each workshop gathered a diverse group of stakeholders, including policymakers, industry representatives, researchers, and civil society organisations, to discuss how proposed policy instruments could support the transition towards a circular and bio-based economy. In particular, the following sectors were tackled at the national level:

- Belgium & Netherlands (UGENT+WR): Chemical, Construction (language: English; participants: 17)
- Germany (DBFZ+BAM): Chemical, Plastics (language: German; participants: 22)
- Italy (FVA+UNITELMA): Plastics, Textile (language: Italian; participants: 34)
- Slovakia (PEDAL): Construction, Textile (language: Slovak; participants: 30)

To complement the workshops and enrich the results further, a survey was conducted in Spain (CIRCE+TECNALIA; language: Spanish; responders: 9) for the Plastics and Textile Sectors (see

Section 4.7). It should be noted that the KPI of 180 participants was not reached due to changes in the organisation of the local events (Belgium and the Netherlands organised a joint workshop, while Spain replaced the event with a survey directed to key stakeholders). Nevertheless, a total of 112 participants ensured the relevance of the results collected and local impacts.

Each workshop was carefully designed and local partners have been supported and empowered by FVA and PEDAL with capacities and tools. Each event began with a set-the-scene session, where invited keynote speakers provided an overview of the *status quo* in the selected sectors. These presentations outlined current trends, policy debates, and sectoral challenges, helping to ground the subsequent discussions in the national context. This was followed by the introduction of the SUSTRACK policy instruments, identified in several rounds of selection and multistakeholder debates, that may be considered to boost the circular bio-based economy transition in the different sectors, explaining both their content and the rationale behind their selection. By distinguishing between direct regulation and market-based instruments, participants were encouraged to reflect on the different logics of coercive versus incentive-based policy approaches. The workshops then moved into **sectoral group discussions**. Stakeholders examined the proposed instruments, providing feedback on their strengths and weaknesses for their implementation in the national contexts, and comments for refinement. By the end of the discussion, participants were asked to prioritise the instruments through a voting procedure. This resulted in a shortlist of priority instruments for each sector. After the group work, all participants reconvened in a plenary session for a capacity building and transfer of knowledge session. This session focused on presenting three key tools and approaches developed within SUSTRACK, designed to foster informed decision-making and systemic transformation: the SUSTRACK Monitoring System, the Systems Thinking and causal loop diagrams, and the System Dynamics (SD) and Green Economy Model (GEM).

The DEPLOY series highlighted the diversity of national circumstances while revealing common needs across Europe. Stakeholders consistently called for a balanced mix of policy tools that combine regulatory clarity, financial support, and innovation incentives. The importance of simplifying administrative procedures, especially for SMEs, and strengthening cooperation between public and private actors was a recurring theme. Participants also stressed that demand-side measures, such as quotas for recycled or bio-based materials, must be supported by investment in infrastructure, skills, and market development.

Despite national specificities, several cross-cutting insights emerged. In Italy, discussions focused on aligning bio-based innovation with industrial competitiveness, particularly in the textile and plastics sectors. Stakeholders in the Netherlands and Belgium underlined the need for integrated sustainability criteria across value chains and stronger policy coherence in construction and chemicals. In Slovakia, the debate centred on the creation of enabling frameworks for circular construction and textiles, including regional hubs and reformed procurement systems. Spain highlighted the importance of linking fiscal measures, such as green VAT and innovation subsidies, with industrial capacity building, while Germany focused on the integration of decarbonisation strategies and the alignment of national actions with the EU Green Deal.

Overall, the DEPLOY phase consolidated SUSTRACK's participatory approach and confirmed the project's value as a policy co-creation platform. By engaging 112 stakeholders across five countries, the workshops generated concrete, context-sensitive insights that strengthened the project's final policy outputs and enhanced their potential for adoption at both national and European levels.

Figure 26 - Some photos and screenshots from the national DEPLOY workshops

Overall conclusions, detailed results of the national workshops and of the Spain Survey are accessible on [SUSTRACK website](#) in the form of factsheets.

4.11 Final event

The SUSTRACK final event, “Projects2Projects: showcasing key results, inspiring new opportunities”, took place online on 28 October 2025 (10:00-12:00 CET), in collaboration with

the [European Bioeconomy Network](#) (EuBioNet). The event was conceived as an opportunity to both showcase SUSTRACK’s main results and foster dialogue and cooperation among Horizon Europe projects addressing standardisation, certification, labelling, and monitoring in the bioeconomy. As SUSTRACK reached its conclusion, the event served as a platform to reflect on the knowledge, tools, exploitable assets, and policy recommendations developed throughout the project, while also looking forward to future opportunities for collaboration and impact.

The programme opened with a presentation of SUSTRACK’s key results, followed by a Projects2Projects roundtable that featured representatives from concluded (or nearly concluded) projects BIOTRANSFORM, STAR4BBS, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, and HARMONITOR (BIOBASEDCERT Cluster), CEE2ACT, ROBIN, 3-CO, and BIORADAR. Each project shared its exploitable results, tools, and lessons learned, highlighting complementarities and synergies with SUSTRACK’s outcomes. A Policy2Projects roundtable followed, bringing together four policymakers from different Directorates-General of the European Commission and one representative of the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE-JU). Their contributions provided forward-looking perspectives on the revision of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy, offering guidance to projects on how to align their activities with future policy priorities. The event concluded with an “open mic” session, where ongoing and newly funded projects – ESCIB, BioFairNet, SYMBA, Stand4Bio, RISERS and WoodStock – presented their work and shared insights on how their initiatives connect with SUSTRACK’s recommendations and results.

By bridging experiences and perspectives across projects and policy levels, the event fostered cross-project collaboration, knowledge exchange, and result exploitation within the European bioeconomy community.

In total, the event (Figure 27) gathered 77 participants, of which 52 external, confirming strong interest in SUSTRACK’s outcomes and their relevance for future European initiatives.

Figure 27 - Some screenshots from the final event

4.12 Lessons learnt

As SUSTRACK concludes, stakeholder engagement stands out as one of the project's valuable and defining elements. The multi-phase engagement process—spanning the INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT, and DEPLOY series—enabled continuous dialogue with a broad and diverse community of policymakers, researchers, industry representatives, and civil society actors. This iterative approach not only validated SUSTRACK's findings but also ensured that project outcomes remained relevant, practical, and grounded in real-world challenges.

The main lesson learnt from SUSTRACK's stakeholder engagement activities, in a period when stakeholders are often overwhelmed by online workshops and events, is that success relies on designing initiatives that are relevant, timely, and provide actionable content. This requires carefully identifying key messages and developing value propositions tailored to different stakeholder groups, in order to ensure meaningful and effective participation.

One key lesson was the importance of designing engagement formats that balance inclusiveness with technical depth. Smaller, thematic workshops encouraged focused and productive exchanges, while larger plenary sessions ensured visibility and cross-sectoral dialogue. This flexible structure proved effective in maintaining participation throughout the project and in capturing perspectives from both experts and generalist audiences.

Another lesson concerned the value of interactive and digital tools. Platforms such as MIRO Boards and Mentimeter significantly improved participation by enabling real-time collaboration and structured feedback, particularly in online and hybrid formats. Their use fostered openness and creativity, helping to translate complex policy discussions into tangible recommendations.

The project also demonstrated that continuity in stakeholder engagement—where each phase builds upon the outcomes of the previous one—creates trust, ownership, and consistency in results. Stakeholders who participated in multiple SUSTRACK events became active contributors, enhancing the project's legitimacy and policy impact. Furthermore, the engagement process highlighted the need for strong facilitation and clear communication. Well-prepared moderators, clear guidance, and concise framing materials helped manage expectations and ensure that discussions remained focused and productive. Finally, SUSTRACK confirmed that meaningful engagement requires not only gathering opinions but also integrating stakeholder input into project outputs. By systematically feeding stakeholder insights into case study analyses, modelling work, and policy recommendations, the project turned consultation into genuine co-creation.

Overall, SUSTRACK's experience shows that sustained, well-structured stakeholder engagement is essential for transforming research outcomes into actionable policies. This approach strengthened the project's credibility, enhanced the usability of its results, and created a foundation for continued collaboration and impact beyond the project's lifetime.

5 COLLABORATION WITH OTHER PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES

SUSTRACK actively promoted collaborations with relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives, capitalising on the extensive experience and networks of its partners in the bioeconomy and bio-based domains. From the outset, all partners contributed by leveraging their contacts to establish synergies with other projects and initiatives.

FVA played a central role in facilitating these collaborations, also through its coordination of the [European Bioeconomy Network \(EuBioNet\)](#), a proactive alliance of more than 150 EU-funded projects and initiatives dedicated to bioeconomy promotion, communication, and support. EuBioNet has been instrumental in maximising joint efforts, fostering knowledge sharing, networking, mutual learning, and enabling the coordination of activities and events.

The main objective of SUSTRACK's collaborative efforts was to work closely with projects addressing **standardisation, certification, labelling, and monitoring**, while at the same time encouraging exchanges with the broader bioeconomy innovation ecosystem.

Throughout the project, SUSTRACK mapped both concluded and ongoing projects, ensuring timely engagement with new EU-funded initiatives as they emerged. This continuous mapping process enabled SUSTRACK to maintain updated connections and reinforce collaboration opportunities.

Collaboration with parallel projects took place at different levels of engagement:

- **Close collaboration with BIOTRANSFORM**, the sister project funded under the same Horizon Europe call (HORIZON-CL6-2022-CIRCBIO-01-03).
- **Knowledge exchange and alignment** with concluded and ongoing projects focusing on standardisation, certification, labelling, and monitoring, as well as **broader collaborations and consultations** with other EU-funded projects in the bioeconomy domain, whenever relevant to SUSTRACK activities and the needs of specific Work Packages.

These efforts ensured that SUSTRACK's outcomes were developed in synergy with the wider EU research and innovation landscape, amplifying impact and fostering long-term sustainability. In total, until the end of the project, **SUSTRACK established collaborations with 33 different projects, at different levels.**

5.1 Clustering activities with BIOTRANSFORM (organised by SUSTRACK)

During the last 18 months, SUSTRACK organised and participated in several activities to liaise with BIOTRANSFORM (parallel project founded under CL6-2022-CIRCBIO-01-03), to increase projects' impact in addressing EU long-term objectives.

The activities organised are summarised in Table 15.

Table 15 - Clustering activities with BIOTRANSFORM, organised by SUSTRACK

CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES WITH BIOTRANSFORM			
Activity and date	Objectives	Target participants (impact)	KPI foreseen
Second Thematic Discussion Meeting, 30 May 2024	SUSTRACK organised a meeting to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> share and discuss the results of the research that both projects were performing on governance and policy recommendations; identify similarities, differences and possible synergies among the results, to avoid overlap and promote mutual learning; discuss and operationalise the next collaboration opportunities. 	7 participants	At least 4 meetings during SUSTRACK
Third Thematic Discussion Meeting, 19 June 2024	SUSTRACK organised a meeting with BIOTRANSFORM and BIORADAR to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> share and discuss the results of the research that projects were performing on tools to monitor the transition; identify similarities, differences and possible synergies among the results, to avoid overlap and promote mutual learning; discuss and operationalise the next collaboration opportunities. 	6 participants	
Fourth Thematic Discussion Meeting, 26 February 2025	BIOTRANSFORM organised a meeting to develop Joint policy recommendations for EU policy makers, to build a set of core, common recommendations stemming from the experience of several European regions. SUSTRACK added to the list of “signatories” of the recommendations drafted by BIOTRANSFORM with the contributions of several projects (BIOTRANSFORM, SUSTRACK, ROBIN, BIOMODEL4REGIONS).	12 participants in total, with 3 representatives from SUSTRACK (UNITELMA, BAM, DBFZ)	

2 nd Thematic mobilisation and mutual learning (MML) workshops, 6 May 2025	See Section 5.2	See Section 5.2	See Section 5.2
SUSTRACK DESIGN and IMPLEMENT Conferences, July-September 2024, February-March 2024	To present and discuss through interactive sessions SUSTRACK results. See Chapter 4 for details.	Several representatives of BIOTRANSFORM project participated in the events	N.A.
SUSTRACK Final Event, 28 October 2025	<p>To maximise the exploitation of results, lessons learnt and recommendations to effectively inspire the newly funded projects in <i>Standardisation, Certification, Labelling, and Monitoring</i>, improving their quality and impact;</p> <p>To facilitate collaboration among ongoing, concluded and recently funded projects; To facilitate awareness and uptake of the main highlights from the revision of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy to inform ongoing and future EU-funded projects.</p>	BIOTRANSFORM representative presented its final results in the roundtable (See Section 4.11)	See Section 4.11

5.1.1 Second Thematic Discussion Meeting (30 May 2024)

On 30 May 2024, SUSTRACK organised a joint Governance Working Group online meeting with BIOTRANSFORM, which brought together representatives from both projects to exchange methodologies, preliminary findings, and approaches on governance, financing, and policy recommendations for the circular bio-based economy. The meeting provided an opportunity to present the ongoing work within SUSTRACK's WP5 and BIOTRANSFORM's governance-related activities, highlighting the common challenges both projects face in translating research evidence into actionable policy recommendations.

Discussions centred on barriers to the transition, the role of policy instruments, and the need to consider both governance and financial mechanisms. Importantly, the exchange laid the

foundation for deeper collaboration, with both projects agreeing to share materials, methodologies, and findings, and to establish thematic working groups to continue discussions.

This initial dialogue proved particularly valuable as it **set the stage for the development of joint policy recommendations**. Building on this collaboration, SUSTRACK and BIOTRANSFORM aligned their work in subsequent activities, including the BIOTRANSFORM meeting on joint policy recommendations (see Section 5.1.3) and the second SUSTRACK mobilisation and mutual learning workshop (see Section 5.2.1). These joint efforts ensured that the policy recommendations emerging from both projects were complementary, consistent, and better positioned to support policymakers in advancing the transition towards a circular bio-based economy.

Figure 28 - Screenshots from the “Second Thematic Discussion Meeting”

5.1.2 Third Thematic Discussion Meeting (19 June 2024)

On 19 June 2024, SUSTRACK organised the “Third Thematic Discussion Meeting” to further align with BIOTRANSFORM. On this occasion, the meeting was also joined by BIORADAR, following their interest expressed during a previous coordination exchange with SUSTRACK. The meeting aimed at sharing progress, discussing methodologies, and exploring synergies across the three projects working on indicators, monitoring tools and sustainability assessments for the circular bioeconomy.

- BIOTRANSFORM presented its six-step assessment framework for identifying transition pathways.
- SUSTRACK introduced the monitoring tool under development, highlighting its dashboard and interactive interface, as well as future improvements (SDG integration, additional data, case-specific uploads, downloadable reports).
- BIORADAR showcased the digital tools being developed (self-assessment tool, SCORECARD linked to SDGs, and a policy tracker), and reported on its ongoing survey on social LCA.

The discussion focused on methodological challenges, including:

- Normalisation and weighting factors;
- Linking indicators with SDGs (need for a common taxonomy across projects);
- Social impact and jobs calculation.

Figure 29 - Screenshot from the “Third Thematic Discussion Meeting”

5.1.3 Fourth Thematic Discussion Meeting (26 February 2025)

As a follow up of the Second Thematic Discussion Meeting, BIOTRANSFORM took the lead in organising a dedicated meeting aimed at developing Joint Policy Recommendations for EU policymakers. The initiative sought to consolidate insights and lessons learned from several European regions into a [coherent set of core common recommendations](#), highlighting practical pathways for advancing the transition towards a circular bioeconomy. The recommendations were enriched through the contributions of multiple projects working under the same Horizon Europe framework, namely BIOTRANSFORM, SUSTRACK, ROBIN, and BIOMODEL4REGIONS. On this occasion, SUSTRACK joined as a signatory, endorsing and contributing to the drafting process by integrating perspectives gathered across its activities.

5.2 Clustering activities with other parallel projects and initiatives in “standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring” and broader collaborations (organised by SUSTRACK)

To maximise the impact of project outcomes by promoting mutual learning and the sharing of common challenges, and boosting the valorisation of existing knowledge, the project promotes collaboration with the most relevant parallel projects in standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring, as well as broader collaborations. This collaboration takes place in two different forms:

- with concluded projects, the SUSTRACK project facilitates the knowledge transfer of exploitable assets to maximise the usage of the outcomes stemming from these projects;
- with ongoing projects, the SUSTRACK project promotes mutual learning, sharing of common challenges, and the valorisation of existing knowledge within parallel projects and initiatives fostering the transition from fossil-based, carbon-intensive systems to circular, bio-based systems.

The list of the 33 projects with which collaborations have been established are presented in Table 16.

Table 16 - Projects identified for collaboration

PROJECTS IDENTIFIED FOR COLLABORATION	
Projects	Type of collaboration established
STAR-ProBio	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
STAR4BBI	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
BIOMONITOR	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
BIOTRANSFORM	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website, 2 nd MML workshop, SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations, SUSTRACK Final Event + other activities reported in Section 5.1 + dissemination activities reported in Section 3.1.3
STAR4BBS	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website, 2 nd MML workshop, SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations, SUSTRACK Final Event + dissemination activities reported in Section 3.1.3
SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website, 2 nd MML workshop, SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations, SUSTRACK Final Event + dissemination activities reported in Section 3.1.3
HARMONITOR	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website, 2 nd MML workshop, SUSTRACK Final Event + dissemination activities reported in Section 3.1.3
CALIMERO	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website, 2 nd MML workshop
ALIGNED	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
BIORECER	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website
3-CO	1 st MML workshop, “Sister project” section on website, 2 nd MML workshop, SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations,

	SUSTRACK Final Event + dissemination activities reported in Section 3.1.3
CEE2ACT	“Sister project” section on website, SUSTRACK Final Event
Circular Cities and Regions Initiative	“Sister project” section on website
BIORADAR	“Sister project” section on website, #1 bilateral meeting + #1 joint meeting with BIOTRANSFORM, SUSTRACK Final Event
ROBIN	“Sister project” section on website, SUSTRACK Final Event + dissemination activities reported in Section 3.1.3
BIO2REG	“Sister project” section on website, bilateral meeting
CheMatSustain	2 nd MML workshop, SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations
ESCIB	2 nd MML workshop, SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations, SUSTRACK Final Event
SYMBA	2 nd MML workshop, SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations, SUSTRACK Final Event
ShapingBio	2 nd MML workshop, SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations, #2 bilateral meetings
BioFairNet	2 nd MML workshop, SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations, SUSTRACK Final Event
ARGONAUT	2 nd MML workshop
BOOST4BIOEAST	2 nd MML workshop, SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations
BEAMING	2 nd MML workshop
MainstreamBio	2 nd MML workshop

BioINSouth	“Sister project” section on website, 2 nd MML workshop, SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations
SYMBIO	2 nd MML workshop
INNOVATE-EU	SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations
COPilot	SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations
Pilot4U	SUSTRACK joint document with policy recommendations
Stand4Bio	SUSTRACK Final Event
RISERS	SUSTRACK Final Event
WoodStock	SUSTRACK Final Event

These objectives have been implemented through the following activities organised by SUSTRACK in the second reporting period (Table 17).

Table 17 - Clustering activities with projects in “Standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring”, organised by SUSTRACK

CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES WITH OTHER PARALLEL PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES IN “STANDARDISATION, CERTIFICATION, LABELLING AND MONITORING”			
Activity and date	Objectives	Target participants (impact)	KPI foreseen
Sister Project section on SUSTRACK website	To leverage on each other’s website for visibility exchange	17 projects	N.A.
2 nd Thematic mobilisation and mutual learning (MML) workshops, 6 May 2025	To provide insights to refine the SUSTRACK results and recommendations, and facilitate the exploitation of the project outcomes.	Representatives of the following projects (18 projects including SUSTRACK, 40 people in total): STAR4BBS, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, HARMONITOR, CheMatSustain,	At least 30 participants in total

		ESCIB, 3-CO, SYMBA, BIOTRANSFORM, ShapingBio, BioFairNet, ARGONAUT, BOOST4BIOEAST, BEAMING, CALIMERO, Mainstreambio, BioINSouth, SYMBIO	
Bilateral meetings with projects	To identify similarities, differences and possible synergies among the results, to avoid overlap and promote mutual learning.	16/05/2024: Meeting SUSTRACK-BIORADAR, 5 participants 14/01/2025 and 27/01/2025: Meeting SUSTRACK-ShapingBio, 4+3 participants 07/02/2025: Meeting SUSTRACK-BIO2REG, 3 participants	N.A.
28/10/2025: SUSTRACK Final Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To maximise the exploitation of results, lessons learnt and recommendations to effectively inspire the newly funded projects in <i>Standardisation, Certification, Labelling, and Monitoring</i>, improving their quality and impact; • To facilitate collaboration among ongoing, concluded and recently funded projects; • To facilitate awareness and uptake of the main highlights from the revision of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy to inform ongoing and 	See Section 4.11	See Section 4.11

	future EU-funded projects.		
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5.2.1 2nd Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshop (6 May 2025)

On 6 May 2025, SUSTRACK, in collaboration with the EuBioNet, organised its 2nd Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshop “Projects4Future”. The event gathered 18 Horizon Europe projects (SUSTRACK, STAR4BBS, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, HARMONITOR, CheMatSustain, ESCIB, 3-CO, SYMBA, BIOTRANSFORM, ShapingBio, BioFairNet, ARGONAUT, BOOST4BIOEAST, BEAMING, CALIMERO, Mainstreambio, BioINSouth, SYMBIO) and engaged over 40 external participants.

The workshop, designed as an interactive session supported by a **MIRO Board**, enabled projects to:

- Map tools and resources developed along key dimensions (indicators, scenarios, standardisation, case studies, capacity building, exploitation);
- Identify **gaps, needs, and challenges** for further implementation and exploitation of these tools;
- Share **lessons learnt** and co-develop **policy recommendations** to inform future research, industrial strategies, and policy agendas.

The consolidated outcomes were presented one week later, on 13 May 2025, at the **BIOBASEDCERT Cluster Final Event** in Brussels by one FVA representative (see Table 7).

A major result of the workshop was the drafting of a [joint document](#), elaborated by FVA on behalf of SUSTRACK and EuBioNet, and enriched with contributions from several projects (ARGONAUT, BioFairNet, BioINSouth, BIOTRANSFORM, CheMatSustain, COPilot, ESCIB, INNOVATE-EU, Pilots4U, ShapingBio, STAR4BBS, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, SYMBA, and 3-CO). The document was [submitted to the European Commission’s public consultation for the revision of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy](#) (“Towards a circular, regenerative and competitive bioeconomy”). The document highlighted common challenges flagged across EU-funded bioeconomy projects, particularly the **lack of harmonised data and methodologies** and the fragmentation of existing tools, which risk limiting their adoption and exploitation. It called for the creation of a **coherent multi-scale data baseline**, the development of **interoperable solutions** integrating existing tools, and the provision of **support services** to ensure their uptake by policymakers and stakeholders. Furthermore, it stressed the need to strengthen the bioeconomy innovation ecosystem, recommending the establishment of **regional innovation brokers or hubs** to facilitate cross-project collaboration, knowledge exchange, foresight exercises, and links to funding opportunities.

These recommendations aim to inform a **harmonised and systemic policy framework**, capable of reducing inefficiencies, promoting synergies, and supporting a just, sustainable, and competitive transition to a circular bio-based economy.

The document also mapped a **list of tools and resources** developed or in development by the participating projects.

activities with stakeholders. Stemming from this meeting, BIORADAR participated in the Third Thematic Discussion Meeting (see Section 5.1.2).

- 14/01/2025: Meeting with ShapingBio (4 participants) aimed at disseminating both projects and exploring collaboration opportunities.
- 27/01/2025: A second meeting with ShapingBio (3 participants) followed up on previous discussions, with SUSTRACK presenting its stakeholder engagement format and sharing knowledge gathered from stakeholder events in an interview format.
- 07/02/2025: Meeting with BIO2REG (3 participants) allowed for an exchange of project approaches: SUSTRACK presented its overall framework, while BIO2REG shared its regional strategy for transitioning carbon-intensive regions towards a bioeconomy, highlighting tools, mentoring, and social aspects of the transition.

Figure 32 - Screenshot of the bilateral meeting with BIO2REG

5.3 Clustering activities with other parallel projects and initiatives in which SUSTRACK representatives participated

SUSTRACK not only organised activities to cluster with other parallel projects and initiatives, but also participated with representatives in several activities organised by those projects, to strengthen the liaisons (Figure 33). A summary of all these activities is listed in Table 18.

Table 18 - Clustering activities with other parallel projects and initiatives in “standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring”, in which SUSTRACK participated

CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES WITH OTHER PARALLEL PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES IN “STANDARDISATION, CERTIFICATION, LABELLING AND MONITORING” IN WHICH SUSTRACK PARTICIPATED	
Activity and date	Objectives
30/05/2024: SUSCER4BIOBASED 3rd Network of Interest meeting	FVA partners attended. Brief update about SUSCER4BIOBASED, shared their indicators framework for certification and main upcoming events.

<p>27/11/2024: Second Multi-Stakeholder Online Meeting of the BioReCer project, titled “Advancing Bio-Based Products Certification: A Collaborative Path Towards Sustainability”</p>	<p>WR and BAM partners attended. Update on BioReCer progresses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardisation Toolkit: overview and key components, • Results of a Delphi Survey: new requirements for enhancing certification schemes; • Policy Brief: Valorisation and use of biological waste to support the European bioeconomy.
<p>22/01/2025: BIORADAR Co-Creation Workshop: Shape the Future of the Circular Bioeconomy</p>	<p>UNITELMA partners attended. Workshop with an interactive session that delved into the BIORADAR Replication Facility, designed to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange in the industrial bio-based sector. Plus, BIORADAR launched a free Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) aimed at equipping professionals, public sector workers, policymakers, citizens with the essential skills needed to understand, for governance and management in the Circular Bioeconomy.</p>

Figure 33 - Screenshots from some clustering activities with other parallel projects and initiatives in which SUSTRACK participated

5.4 Clustering activities with other initiatives in the bioeconomy

In parallel with the above-mentioned focused collaborations and activities, SUSTRACK encouraged collaboration with the wider community of the bioeconomy innovation ecosystem, and specifically, the collaboration with relevant initiatives. These collaborations were also facilitated by [EuBioNet](#), in which [SUSTRACK has been partner](#) since the beginning of the project.

5.4.1 Clustering activities with ECOSYSTEMEX initiative

In February 2023, SUSTRACK became one of the founding members of the [ECOSYSTEMEX initiative](#). Bringing together 60+ EU-funded projects focused on textile sustainability, ECOSYSTEMEX, the European Community of Practice for a Sustainable Textile Ecosystem, was officially launched in early 2023 with the goal of fostering collaboration in the field of textile sustainability and circularity.

A joint initiative of the European Commission’s Research Executive Agency (REA), the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA), and the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint

Undertaking, and facilitated by the Textile ETP, this network of textile circularity projects seeks to establish a long-term community of practice, promoting collaboration across project consortia and ensuring impact that extends beyond the lifetime of individual projects.

In this context, SUSTRACK joined several ECOSYSTEM Working Groups (HG1 - Research and Innovation Gaps and Needs; HG2 - Joint dissemination, which meet periodically, TG1 - Environmental Assessment & Product Environmental Footprint; TG3 - Ecodesign for Safe and Sustainable Materials, Products & Processes) and participated in several activities organised by ECOSYSTEM both in the first and in the second reporting period, with different objectives:

- Dissemination and communication purposes (specifically described in Chapter 3);
- Being updated about activities and results by the other members;
- Establish synergies among projects involved in ECOSYSTEM.

A summary of the activities done in the second reporting period (Figure 34) is reported in Table 19.

Table 19 - Summary of the activities with ECOSYSTEM (not including the dissemination and communication activities)

ACTIVITIES WITH ECOSYSTEM (NOT INCLUDING DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES)		
Activity and date	Objectives	Target participants (impact)
11/04/2025: HG2 - Joint Dissemination	Shared ECOSYSTEM news, how to share events and activities with them. Presented the ECOSYSTEM conference 2025.	16 participants
08/07/2025: ECOSYSTEM Technical Working Group TG 1 meeting - Environmental Assessment & Product Environmental Footprint	Represent SUSTRACK project in the working group meetings, present information about our project and our expertise related to LCA and circularity assessment, participate in discussions concerning methodologies and tools used in sustainability assessment and LCA methods used	ECOSYSTEM members (about 20 people) with expertise on topic of environmental assessment

Figure 34 - Screenshot from an HG2 meeting with ECOSYSTEX

6 NEXT STEPS AND CONCLUSIONS

This final deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the dissemination, communication, and stakeholder engagement activities carried out throughout the SUSTRACK project from M19 to M36. It highlights the tools, materials, campaigns, and events implemented to promote the project, as well as the strategies and key messages adapted to each project phase.

FVA, as the dissemination and communication leader, and PEDAL, as the stakeholder engagement leader, have ensured continuous partner involvement and empowerment, fostering active sharing of content and information across networks. The monitoring tools implemented throughout the project allowed for tracking progress, measuring impact, and adjusting approaches as needed.

Overall, the activities presented in this report demonstrate SUSTRACK's effective approach to promoting project results, engaging stakeholders, and supporting the transition towards a circular bio-based economy, providing a solid foundation for future initiatives, collaborations and results exploitation beyond the project's duration.

Project Consortium

